

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.1402 Max: 63.4272	1250 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: D0189-0197	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Dividing wall between rooms 1 + 3	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX					
<i>Anthropic</i>	<i>Geological</i>	<i>Organic</i>	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%					
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive					
			<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Compaction</td> <td>Color</td> </tr> <tr> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) </td> </tr> </table>		Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1183, 1185
Is covered by: 1016	Covers: 1205
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

Pictures D0189-0197 are of Room 1

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: Near center at southern edge of excavation

Shape: Linear

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight</p> <p>Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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D0189-0197

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: **E-W**

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: **4.12 m long, average block size 50cm x 40cm x 27cm**

Description:

Linear partition wall within structure, made of tufo blocks. Single course preserved. Gap present in the west, near where wall approaches wall 1183. Wall sits on soil (SU _____).

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1250 is a partition wall built after the exterior walls of the building had been constructed. It separated the larger space into two rooms, room 1 + room 2. The gap in the west may represent a doorway, but could also be the result of robbing activity - several other robbed trenches are nearby.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by **J. FARR**

on **26.07.2010**

Revised by **CHM**

on **27.07.2010**

PDFd by **JJM**

on **28/7/2010**

Entered by

on